

Experimental modeling of mooring systems for floating marine energy concepts

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Abstract

New floating devices are emerging thanks to a highly active marine renewable energy sector. These concepts, featuring floating offshore wind installations as well as other projects in the wave energy sector require innovative mooring systems. Therefore, a complete analysis of this element is required to achieve a successful design.

This paper investigates the behaviour of mooring systems based on catenary configuration thanks to a detailed experimental program. Tests to characterize the properties of the mooring lines, and geotechnical and hydrodynamic trials were also performed on a 1:40 laboratory scale. Mooring truncation problem is normally faced by the researchers working on model testing of mooring lines in deep water, because the depth of the lab is typically small. However, it does not seem to be a problem for offshore floating renewable energy devices which are usually in relatively shallow water. The influence of catenary weight, imposed displacements at the fairlead, wave-current loads and different types of sea bottom friction on the mooring systems were analysed in terms of tensions, movements and shape of force-displacement curve. However, scaling of the sea bottom and the mooring line interaction is a challenge. Although the damping effect was investigated and compared under different movement conditions, the conclusions achieved can be upscale to real scale but it must be noticed that there are limitations due to scale effect issues. A total of 111 tests were performed. The influence of the hydrodynamic inertia and drag is negligible on long wave and slow motions, while they have more importance during shorter waves and quick motions. The results reveal the importance of acceleration in the movement being possible to distinguish dynamic and quasi-static performance depending on the acceleration of the mooring line.

Keywords: Flume, Experiment, Mooring lines, Dynamic, Acceleration

1. Introduction

Deep water areas represent the future of renewable marine developments due to the presence of greater and better wind and wave energy resources, among numerous other reasons. Because of this, the number of floating marine energy concepts has increased in recent years with new prototypes of wind floating platforms [1], multi-use platforms [2] and wave energy converters [3]. These floating structures are generally secured by mooring systems. The main function of a mooring system is to restrict the movements of the floating structure and to resist environmental actions.

Mooring systems are constituted by one or several lines anchored to the seabed which are connected to a floating platform at a point called a fairlead. Essentially, three different types of configurations can be found: catenary, semi-taut, and taut mooring lines. Most of them are comprised of steel chain links and steel wires. However, synthetic fiber ropes are routinely used in semi-taut and taut mooring systems.

The catenary configuration is one of the most common. A catenary is the curve that a hanging chain, cable or rope shows under its own weight when it is supported only at its ends. Catenary systems always have enough line length resting on the seabed to avoid vertical forces on the anchoring system.

Mooring systems are an essential part of floating structures to ensure their survivability and stability. Moreover, they constitute an important element in the cost breakdown, typically about 8% of the capital expenditure of a typical marine platform installation [4], and they therefore have a large impact on the cost of energy.

Experimental studies of mooring line dynamics have been carried out by several researchers. Lindahl [5] investigated the behavior of the pitch of a mooring line using a chain which was excited by vertical circular motions with various radii and periodicities, measuring the force in the upper end of the chain. Simos et al [6] continued analysing pitch behavior, adding current effects to the mooring line dynamics using a compound line (chain and wire rope). They included different combinations of the amplitude and the frequency of motion in order to generate a set of experimental results of the dynamic tension acting on the top of a mooring line model with circular harmonic motions imposed at its top. Azcona et al [7] studied surge behavior on mooring lines. A mooring line was excited with prescribed motions producing different dynamic conditions, including harmonic response, loss of tension, and snap loading, focusing on the shape of the line and the tension at the fairlead. Taking into account all the previous research, there are still some knowledge gaps that need to be addressed, for example: the influence of weight, the sea bottom friction,

59 the natural loads (waves, currents and wave-current) and the prescribed movements at the fairlead position
60 on mooring lines.

61 The aim of this paper is to experimentally analyse the dynamic behavior of different mooring lines and
62 the impact of weight and sea bottom friction, and the importance of acceleration on the catenary considering
63 different fairlead movements not yet analysed in the literature.

64 The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of the experimental test campaign,
65 detailing the test facility, the physical model, the experimental set up, the monitoring system, and the
66 actuators and mechanisms used. Section 3 describes the experimental tests done to analyse the mooring
67 systems, focusing on the physical, mechanical, geotechnical, and hydrodynamic characterization. Section
68 4 presents a discussion, divided into individual analysis and aggregated analysis from all the test results.
69 The paper is closed with some conclusion on the previous work.

70 **2. Experimental test campaign**

71 **2.1 Wave Flume Characteristics**

72 Mooring line tests were performed in the wave and currents flume known as the COCoTsu, managed
73 by the Environmental Hydraulics Institute of Cantabria, shown in Figure 3. It is 56 m long, 2 m wide and
74 2.4 m high. It is equipped with a 2 m stroke piston-type paddle moved by a hydraulic actuator including an
75 active wave absorption system.

76 The maximum possible wave height at the installation is approximately 0.7 m, depending on the wave
77 period and the water depth. The maximum operating depth for higher waves is 1.35 m.

78 The testing area of this flume is 24 m long, with its side walls and bottom constructed of glass all along
79 the testing section. A passive wave absorber built of vertical porous metal screens occupies the last 10 m
80 of the wave flume.

81 **2.2 Physical model**

82 Taking into account typical mooring line lengths in marine renewable applications and the wave flume
83 characteristics, the selected scale used to perform the tests was 1:40. Froude's laws of similitude [8] were
84 applied to the mooring dimensions in order to accurately reproduce the hydrodynamic behavior.

85 The scale laws according to Froude maintain the relationship between the inertial and gravitational
86 forces in the model and the prototype. The relationship between the length (λ), gravity (λ_G) and velocity
87 (λ_v) scale is shown in Equation 1.

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$$\frac{\lambda_V}{\sqrt{\lambda_G \lambda}} = 1$$

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Equation 1. Relationship scale according to Froude.

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Table 1 shows the main Froude laws of similitude.

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Physical Magnitude	Dimension	Conversion Factor Froude
Length	L	λ
Area	L^2	λ^2
Mass	M	λ^3
Volume	L^3	λ^3
Time	T	$\sqrt{\lambda}$
Velocity	$L * T^{-1}$	$\sqrt{\lambda}$
Acceleration	$L * T^{-2}$	1
Moments	$M * L$	λ^4
Pressure	$M * L^{-1} * T^{-2}$	λ
Energy	$M * L^2 * T^{-2}$	λ^4
Force	$M * L * T^{-2}$	λ^3

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Table 1. Froude laws of similitude.

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This paper presents all results in model scale. If it is desirable to obtain the results in prototype scale

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enough with applying the Equation 2.

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$$\text{Prototype Magnitud} = \text{Conversion Factor Froude} * \text{Model Magnitud}$$

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Equation 2. Conversion Prototype-Model

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The characteristics of the steel chains selected for the experiments are displayed in Table 2. One of the

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most important parameters for catenary modelling is the weight per unit length, although there are other

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significant parameters such as axial stiffness and diameter. A calibrated spring was inserted in each line in

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order to simulate the real axial stiffness (Figure 2).

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DIAMETER, d (mm)		t (mm)		b (mm)		LENGHT (m)		MASS (kg/m)	
Model	Prototype	Model	Prototype	Model	Prototype	Model	Prototype	Model	Prototype
1.6	64	13	520	8	320	7.305	292.2	0.047	75.2
2.5	100	16	640	9.5	380	7.305	292.2	0.115	184
3	120	18	720	11	440	7.305	292.2	0.162	259.2

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Table 2. Experimental geometric and mass properties

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Figure 1. The shape of the chains

Figure 2. Springs in the mooring lines

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2.3 Experimental set up

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A sketch of the plan and cross-section views of the flume and the physical model is shown in Figure 3.

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Three mooring lines (featured in Table 2) were tested in each test in order to experimentally analyse the effect of mooring line weight on the dynamic performance of the line. The mooring lines were submerged in the flume and they were anchored by means of heavy steel plate to the bottom and moored to a movable fairlead. The distance between the anchor and fairlead was 6.97 m and the water depth was 1.35 m. The fairlead was located 0.15 m below the water surface.

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Figure 3. Plan and cross-section views of the general set up

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2.4 Monitoring system

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The reference system was located at the anchor of the central mooring line in the flume.

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The set of sensors and gauges employed can be seen in Figure 4. Six wave gauges (Figure 5a) were used to separate the free surface record into incident and reflected waves [9]. The water current profile was measured by five ADV's. The vertical distance between ADV's was 0.25 m measured from flume bottom (Figure 5b). Movements in the catenary were recorded using the underwater motion capture system, Qualisys [10]. This system uses markers to capture the movements. Markers are made of polystyrene

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137 hemispheres covered with a special retro-reflective tape. Six markers (Figure 6) separated by 0.2 m from
 138 fairlead were used along each mooring line. In order to compensate for the extra displacement caused by
 139 the markers in the mooring line, an equivalent weight was placed to eliminate their effect, in this case, 0.9
 140 grams.

141 Mooring line loads were measured using axial load cells. The loads cells were installed at the fairlead
 142 position using one cell per line (Figure 5c).

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Figure 4. Measurement instrument in the flume

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Figure 5. a) Akamina AWP-24 b) Acoustic Doppler Velocimeters (ADV) c) Futek LSB210

Figure 6. Qualisys system markers

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2.5 Actuators and mechanisms: prescribed displacements

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154 With the aim of simulating the representative movements of a floating offshore platform, two
155 mechanisms were built. Firstly, a rotating machine was designed to describe imposed movements in roll
156 and yaw, shown in Figure 8. A gear system was chosen to transmit the movement between the engine and
157 the structure. The rotation machine is an aluminum structure with three steel discs which reproduces the
158 circular movements, roll and yaw, by placing the discs in two positions (horizontal and vertical). It is
159 possible to test all three mooring lines at the same time. The movement is generated by the torque produced
160 by the engine (MDrive 34: MDI1frd34c7 EQ) and transmitted by a series of gears and bearings. A
161 crankshaft with a pulley scheme recreates the pitch movement (Figure 9). Finally, a linear actuator was
162 used to reproduce surge and heave movements (Figure 7). The linear actuator (Bosch: EMC80) was able to
163 produce an acceleration of 9.5 m/s^2 with 600 N at maximum power. An aluminium structure was designed
164 and constructed to allow its placement in the flume. The actuator is supported by a central bar which moves
165 along with it thanks to guide rails with bearings. Three vertical bars were attached to the control bar to
166 adjust the underwater position of each mooring line.

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Figure 7. View of the linear actuator

Figure 8. View of the rotation machine

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Figure 9. View of the crankshaft

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3. Description of the experimental tests

178 Three different set of experiments were carried out: 1) physical and mechanical experiments, 2)
179 geotechnical experiments and 3) hydrodynamic experiments.

3.1 Physical and mechanical characterization

181 The mooring lines (Table 2) were simulated by means of chains. The physical properties were
182 characterized by different trials. The main parameter which influences the behavior of the mooring line is
183 its weight. However, there are other, albeit less important parameters such as the axial stiffness and the
184 diameter. In order to calculate the stiffness and the equivalent diameter, tensile test and water displacement
185 methods were utilized.

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187 The tensile test involves placing a specimen of the chain in the testing machine and slowly stretching
 188 it until it fractures. During this process, the elongation is recorded against the force applied. Three test per
 189 chain were done. A summary of the results is shown in Figure 10 and summarized in Table 3.

190 In general, the axial stiffness observed was higher than the axial stiffness of the prototype. The elastic
 191 modulus is compared with the DNV formulation [11] for the three mooring line grades in Table 4. In
 192 general, the results are one order of magnitude higher than the DNV formulation. Because of that, calibrated
 193 springs were required in order to simulate the real axial stiffness.

194 As mentioned in the previous paragraph, laboratory chains do not accurately represent the real
 195 stiffness of most of the common chains used in offshore marine structures. Because of this, it is a good
 196 practice to include a calibrated spring (k_s) in the line in order to replicate the real stiffness. Accordingly,
 197 the real stiffness will be a result of two stiffnesses, one from the mooring line (chain) and the other from
 198 the spring. Considering the force in the line, F , and the displacement, δ , one way of calculating the spring
 199 stiffness, using compatibility equations when the real stiffness of the prototype (k_p) and the stiffness of the
 200 model (k_m) are known, is the following:

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$$F = k_p \delta_p \quad F = k_m \delta_m = k_s \delta_s \quad \delta_p = \delta_m + \delta_s$$

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$$k_s = \frac{k_p k_m}{k_m - k_p}$$

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Equation 3. Compatibility equations to obtain the spring stiffness

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The spring stiffness used in each line is indicated in Table 3.

PROPERTIES	DIAMETER (mm)		
	1.6	2.5	3
INITIAL LENGTH (mm)	514.17	500.1	491.8
BREAKING LOAD (N)	358	4200	7210
ELONGATION (m)	0.00342	0.03613	0.05277
STIFFNESS (N/m)	119548	489614	740745
ELASTIC MODULUS (N/m ²)	7.35 x 10 ⁹	1.56 x 10 ¹⁰	7.72 x 10 ¹⁰
SPRING (N/m)	975	1987	2772
EQUIVALENT DIAMETER (m)	0.0033	0.0045	0.0052
ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS (TEMPERATURE/RELATIVE HUMIDITY)	18.1 °C 86.1%		

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Table 3. Physical and mechanical characterization of the chains

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Figure 10. Tensile test: load curve

PROTOTYPE SCALE	DIAMETER (mm)		
	64	100	120
ELASTIC MODULUS (N/m ²)			
LABORATORY	2.94 x 10 ¹¹	6.23 x 10 ¹¹	6.90 x 10 ¹¹
DNV: R3	5.14 x 10 ¹⁰	5.00 x 10 ¹⁰	4.92 x 10 ¹⁰
DNV: R4	5.29 x 10 ¹⁰	5.20 x 10 ¹⁰	5.15 x 10 ¹⁰
DNV: R5	5.79 x 10 ¹⁰	5.67 x 10 ¹⁰	5.60 x 10 ¹⁰

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Table 4. Elastic modulus: Laboratory & DNV

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3.2 Geotechnical characterization

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The Shields number criteria was used in order to represent the size of the gravel at laboratory scale

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[12]. The inception of movement is considered to be the same if critical Shields numbers remain equal in

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both the prototype and the scale model. The relation is:

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$$N_D = N_L * N_{\Delta}^{-2.083} = 43.5$$

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$$N_D = \text{grain size scale} \quad N_L = \text{Length scale} \quad N_{\Delta} = \text{Submerged density scale}$$

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Equation 4. Grain size scale

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The grain size distribution is shown in Figure 11. The grain mean diameter (D_{50}) is 0.13 mm which

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corresponds in real scale to 5.65 mm, a fine gravel.

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Figure 11. Granulometric curve: Grain size distribution

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The sand bottom friction was obtained from a drag test. This test is based on dragging a chain at constant velocity using a carriage located at the top of the flume. By measuring the drag force during the test it is possible to determine the friction coefficient. The obtained friction coefficient over the glass bottom surface (without sand) was 0.24, and with sand 0.7.

Figure 12. Drag test

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3.3 Hydrodynamic characterization: dynamic performance tests

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Different dynamic conditions were simulated in order to characterize the mooring lines. Different combinations between fairlead position and ocean loads were tested as well. The test plan (Table 5) was divided into two types of tests: one with imposed movements at the fairlead and the other with hydrodynamic loads (wave, current, wave-current). In addition the effect of sea bottom friction was also studied thanks to a sandpit included in the second half of the experiments.

TEST PLAN			Ocean loads			
			Without loads	Wave	Current	Wave-current
Fairlead position	Static	Fixed	x	x	x	x
	Dynamic (imposed movements)	Surge	x	-	x	-
		Heave	x	-	x	-
		Roll	x	-	-	-
		Pitch	x	-	-	-
		Yaw	x	-	-	-

Table 5. Test plan

Different sea states were selected in order to observe the hydrodynamic response: regular waves and irregular sea states. A set of regular waves without imposed movements were performed. Regular wave tests were carried out for different wave heights (0.075 m and 0.150 m) and several periods, from 0.95 s to 2.21 s at model scale.

Irregular tests were also performed without imposed movements, covering significant wave heights between 0.15 m and 0.225 m, and peak periods between 1.42 s and 2.06 s.

SEA STATES			
Waves	H-Hs (m)	T-Tp (s)	H-Hs /L
Regular	0.075	0.95-1.26-1.58-1.90-2.21	0.053-0.030-0.020-0.014-0.011
Regular	0.150	0.95-1.26-1.58-1.90-2.21	0.106-0.061-0.039-0.029-0.023
Irregular	0.150	1.42	0.048
Irregular	0.175	1.9	0.034
Irregular	0.225	2.06	0.038

Table 6. Wave tests

Finally, imposed movement tests were performed in the following degrees of freedom: surge, heave, roll, yaw and pitch. Surge movements were tested with three different amplitudes: 0.0375 m, 0.075 m and 0.125 m. Periods between 0.79 s and 7.91 s were tested for all amplitudes considered. Heave movement tests were performed for two amplitudes, 0.0375 m and 0.075 m with periods between 0.79 s and 3.48 s. Additionally, tests with movements and current (0.08 m/s) were carried out as well. The amplitude was 0.075 m for surge movements and 0.0375 m for heave. A total number of 55 tests were carried out for surge and heave. Table 7 shows a summary of the surge and heave tests.

IMPOSED MOVEMENTS		
Movements	2A (m)	T (s)
Surge	0.075	0.79-1.58-2.37-3.16-4.74-6.32-7.91
	0.150	0.79-1.58-2.37-3.16-4.74-6.32-7.91
	0.250	0.79-1.58-2.37-3.16-4.74-6.32-7.91
Heave	0.075	0.79-1.26-1.58-1.90-2.21-2.53-2.85-3.16-3.48
	0.150	0.79-1.26-1.58-1.90-2.21-2.53-2.85-3.16-3.48

Table 7. Linear imposed movements

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286 Imposed rotations were carried out to simulate roll, pitch and yaw movements. The radius was the same
287 for roll and yaw and different for pitch due to the rotating machine used. A wide range of velocities were
288 used for each degree of freedom. The specific characteristics of each test are shown in Table 8. A total of
289 15 tests were done for roll, yaw and pitch.

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IMPOSED MOVEMENTS		
Rotations	Radius (m)	Velocity (rad/s)
Roll	0.100	0.123-0.368-0.614-1.227-1.841-2.454
Yaw	0.100	0.123-0.614-1.227
Pitch	0.120	0.061-0.184-0.307-0.368-0.920-1.227

Table 8. Imposed movements rotations

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293 The effect of sea bottom friction was studied for several degrees of freedom: surge, heave and pitch. A
294 sand pit 0.11 m thick (Figure 13) was poured within the flume on which the mooring lines were placed.
295 The same cases of the previously imposed movements were simulated.

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Figure 13. Sandpit in mooring line tests

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4. Results

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All test results are presented at model scale. Firstly, tests were analysed individually and finally they

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were sorted by type of test to obtain general conclusions about the performance obtained.

303 In the following sections, the behaviour of the mooring lines including tensions at the fairlead,
 304 movements and energy absorbed is analysing under different test hypotheses: imposed movements,
 305 imposed movements with currents, wave and wave-current with the fairlead in static position and, finally,
 306 imposed movements with sandy sea bottom.

307 4.1 Imposed movements

308 Displacements and tensions were measured in each mooring line for each test. An important
 309 magnitude related to displacements and tensions is the amount of energy absorbed by the mooring line. The
 310 energy can be calculated using Equation 5 where \vec{F} and $\vec{\delta}$ represent the tension and the displacement at
 311 the fairlead, respectively.

$$E = \oint \vec{F} d\vec{\delta}$$

312
 313 Equation 5. Energy in the mooring line
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315 If the tension-displacement pair for each time step on the fairlead is represented, the hysteresis cycle is
 316 obtained. The area enclosed by the hysteresis loop represents the energy dissipated in each cycle. Figure 14
 317 and Figure 15 present examples of the results obtained for the surge imposed movement tests, with
 318 amplitude 75 mm / period 1.58 s and amplitude 75 mm / period 7.91 s, respectively.
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 321 Figure 14. Test: Surge (amplitude 75 mm / period 1.58 s). Displacement and tension series. Hysteresis cycle
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Figure 15. Test: Surge (amplitude 75 mm / period 7.91 s). Displacement and tension series. Hysteresis cycle

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From the comparison of Figure 14 and Figure 15 it is concluded that:

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- Firstly, the displacement and tension series are out of phase in tests with short periods. However, they are in phase for long period tests.

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- Secondly, the magnitude of the tension shows higher values in the shorter periods than in the larger ones. This phenomenon is due to the importance of the accelerations which are analysed in the next section.

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- Finally, the hysteresis cycle in short period tests encloses a greater amount of energy than in long period tests. The energy is 0.363 J, 0.291 J and 0.211 J for diameters of 3 mm, 2.5 mm and 1.6 mm, respectively in the surge test with amplitude 75 mm and period 1.58 s, whereas it is 0.013 J, 0.005 J and 0.005 J respectively in the surge test with amplitude 75 mm and period 7.91 s. Therefore, shorter periods dissipate more energy than longer ones.

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The analysis of trajectories shows the same pattern in all tests. Points near the fairlead show similar movement patterns as the fairlead. Conversely, deeper point movements are practically vertical. Figure 16, Figure 17 and Figure 18 show the trajectories of all the markers for the roll, surge and pitch tests. The M1 marker is located 0.2 meters from the fairlead position and the rest of the markers are similarly situated with 0.2 m between them. (i.e. M2 is located 0.4 m from the fairlead, M3 is 0.6 m away etc.) Roll movement is imposed at the fairlead as a circular movement in the YZ-plane. The markers tend to describe elliptical movements in the YZ-plane and the XY-plane, and vertical movement in the XZ-plane. Similar results are obtained for the pitch movement, although the semi-axes are the shortest and the longest in the horizontal

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344 and vertical directions respectively. If a surge movement is applied at the fairlead, the trajectories of the
 345 markers near to the fairlead are horizontal but become almost vertical in the deeper markers.
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Figure 16. Test: Roll (0.123 rad/s). Trajectories in the XY-plane, the YZ-plane and the XZ-plane

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Figure 17. Test: Surge (amplitude 125 mm / period 7.91 s). Trajectories in the XZ-plane

Figure 18. Test: Pitch (0.0614 rad/s). Trajectories in the XZ-plane

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356 Results for the surge imposed movements are presented in Figure 19 through Figure 22. In Figure 19,
357 the energy absorbed is shown according to the different periods and amplitudes tested for each mooring
358 line. The amount of energy absorbed depends on weight and movement (amplitude and period). In general,
359 the more weight, the more amplitude and the shorter the period, the more energy absorbed by the line.
360 Similar effects are found in heave imposed movements. It is worth noting that when movement periods are
361 short, the energy absorbed is higher, up to a certain period, after which the energy absorbed tends to
362 decrease and there is no difference between line weight and movement period. This period is 3 s, 2.25 s
363 and 1.5 s for amplitudes of 0.125 m, 0.075 m and 0.0375 m, respectively. Therefore, the period varies with
364 the amount of energy introduced into the system.

365 After those periods, the energy absorbed is practically the same in all the lines regardless of weight.
366 The movements and tensions on the fairlead tend to be in phase, the shape of the hysteresis cycle changes
367 from a closed contour to a line, and the mooring line dynamic effects due to acceleration are less prominent.
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Figure 19. Test: surge movement. Energy absorbed by the different lines

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372 In Figure 20 to Figure 22, the maximum and minimum value of the tension series according to the
373 different periods and amplitudes tested for each mooring line are shown. In all the cases, it is important to
374 note that there is a certain period after which the maximum and minimum tension are constant. This value
375 is coincident with the value of the absorbed energy threshold. Therefore, maximum and minimum loads
376 depend on the weight and the stroke, up to a certain period. Then, the mooring load becomes constant and
377 only depends on line weight. The maximum and minimum values of the line forces are observed for long
378 amplitudes and short periods reaching, eventually, snap loads, for example in the case with amplitude 0.125
379 m and period 0.79 s.

380 When the tension becomes practically constant it means that the acceleration is of little importance to
381 the dynamics of the line. These points are coincident with the points from which the energy is the same in
382 all the mooring lines.

Figure 20. Test: surge movement (amplitude 0.125 m). Tension series

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Figure 21. Test: surge movement (amplitude 0.075 m). Tension series

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Figure 22. Test: surge movement (amplitude 0.0375 m). Tension series

391 Figure 23 displays the energy absorbed by the lines in a heave movement with amplitude 0.075 m. In
392 addition, the evolution of the hysteresis curve ($F-\delta$) is also presented. From these results, it is important to
393 highlight that the maximum tension peak shows some variation from shorter to longer periods. The
394 maximum tension peak can be observed before the maximum stroke for shorter periods while it is achieved
395 at the maximum stroke for long periods.

396 Short periods are highly influenced by accelerations whereas accelerations of long periods decrease in
397 importance; tensions and movements tend to move together in phase and there is less energy absorbed. In
398 general, the energy absorbed by heavier lines is greater except when the maximum force corresponds to the
399 maximum amplitude at which point the energy absorbed by the three mooring lines is practically equal
400 regardless of weight.

Figure 23. Test: heave movement. Hysteresis cycle evolution

4.2 Importance of the accelerations

In order to verify the importance of the accelerations, x and z (positive and negative in both cases) accelerations are shown for each mooring line marker, as well as the feedback signal at the fairlead position. Acceleration analysis was done for the heaviest chain (0.162 kg/m, 3 mm in diameter) and for surge tests using an amplitude of 75 mm. In Figure 24 and Figure 25, the evolution of the x and z accelerations is shown, respectively, for all markers depending on the period test and a parameter characteristic of the acceleration. Mean, significant, and maximum and minimum values are considered.

When accelerations in the x -direction are analysed, it is possible to conclude that points located near to the fairlead, specifically M1, M2, and M3, have relevant accelerations whilst points located deeper show smaller accelerations.

In contrast, when accelerations in the z -direction are analysed, it is possible to verify that the deeper nodes have higher accelerations until they become zero at the position of the fairlead. It is important to note that accelerations in the x -direction are smaller than the accelerations in the z -direction. This is due to the movements' asymmetry, as can be seen in Figure 26, where z -movements show wider and flatter troughs, therefore positive and negative accelerations in the z -direction are different (non-symmetrical) and accelerations in the z -direction are greater than the accelerations in the x -direction due to the slope of the movement.

From the analysis of the acceleration figures, we can conclude that there are two clear regions. A first region from low periods up to 2.25 s where the mooring line is fully dynamic, and another region, with periods longer than 2.25 s, when the mooring line shows a more quasi-static response.

424 This limit is related to the energy absorbed in the hysteresis curve and tension. Below 2.25 s the energy
 425 absorbed depends on the movement period, while above 2.25 s it tends to be constant.

426 Therefore, the fundamental variable which governs the behavior of the mooring line is acceleration.
 427 Tensions on the line depend on it. The influence of the acceleration on the tension is reflected in Figure 21;
 428 it shows that, for values greater than 2.25 s, the tension is constant and, therefore, that the influence of the
 429 acceleration on the tension is practically non-existent. In addition, from the tension, the energy absorbed is
 430 obtained by the mooring line through the hysteresis cycle. Precisely at 2.25 s, the energy of the three lines
 431 is similar. The maximum and minimum acceleration is 0.50 m/s^2 and -0.50 m/s^2 respectively in the x-
 432 direction and 0.75 m/s^2 and -0.93 m/s^2 respectively in the z-direction. These acceleration values delineate
 433 the boundary between a quasi-static analysis and a dynamic analysis. A quasi-static analysis is adequate
 434 when acceleration is lower than 0.50 m/s^2 in the x-direction and 1 m/s^2 in the z-direction.

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436

437 Figure 24. Test: surge movement (amplitude 0.075 m). Evolution of the accelerations in the x-direction for all the
 438 markers

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Figure 25. Test: surge movement (amplitude 0.075 m). Evolution of the accelerations in the z-direction for all the markers

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Figure 26. Test: surge movement (amplitude 0.075 m). Movements in the x-direction and the z-direction

448 4.3 Imposed movement and current

449 In order to investigate the effects of a current on the movement of a mooring line, tests with movement
450 and currents were carried out.

451 Current effects are shown in Figure 27 and Figure 28. In Figure 27, the energy absorbed is presented
452 for the lines under two different conditions: a 0.075 meter surge imposed movement with and without

453 current. The main differences are found in the shortest periods where the mooring line exhibits a dynamic
 454 behaviour. In general, it can be observed that the dissipated energy per cycle is higher in the case with
 455 current. Particularly, it increases up to 80% in the test at 0.79 s. Energy dissipation tends to be zero for long
 456 periods. With regard to tensions (Figure 28), the experiment confirmed that the mooring line tension
 457 increases due to current action. Differences of between 6% and 13% for maximum values and between 3%
 458 and 4% for minimum values were observed.

459 According to Morison's formula [13], the tension of the line is influenced by the drag coefficient and
 460 the square of the velocity. Taking this into account, the more significant effects are found in the short
 461 periods due to the higher velocities, which are increased/decreased by the current velocity.
 462

463
 464 Figure 27. Test: surge movement-current. Comparison between the energy absorbed by the different lines
 465

466
 467 Figure 28. Test: surge movement/current. Comparison between tension series

468 **4.4 Wave and wave-current**

469 Experiments were done keeping the position of the fairlead fixed in the presence of hydrodynamic
 470 excitation forces (waves and wave-currents). Figure 29 shows the dynamic tension results (maximum and
 471 mean amplitude) caused by regular and irregular waves for each mooring line. All the sea states tested are
 472 depicted on each graph. The dynamic tension results are represented by circles for regular waves and
 473 squares for irregular waves.

474
 475 Figure 29. Test: regular and irregular waves. Tension

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 477
 478 In general, it is necessary to emphasise that the tension variations are small and that the difference
 479 between the average and maximum tension is negligible when compared to the static tension. Similar results
 480 were obtained for waves and current. Therefore, hydrodynamic dynamic loads are not the dominant factor,
 481 despite the uncertainties that can be associated with the Reynolds number. For this reason, the Reynolds
 482 number is calculated at both the model scale and the prototype scale in order to find possible differences in
 483 the drag coefficient given by the DNV standard [14]. Discrepancies were obtained in the drag coefficient
 484 as is shown in Table 9. In this table, The Reynolds number for both the model scale and the prototype scale
 485 were calculated for a regular sea state ($H = 0.15$ m and $T = 0.95$ s). In addition, the drag coefficient values
 486 as a function of the Reynolds number are indicated according to the DNV standard, although it does not
 487 include all possible Reynolds numbers. It can be verified that there are slight discrepancies in the drag
 488 coefficient when the model scale or the prototype scale are considered.

489

H= 0.15 m T=0.95 s	REYNOLDS NUMBER		DRAG COEFFICIENT (DNV) Cd		
DIAMETER (mm)	MODEL SCALE	PROTOTYPE SCALE	REYNOLDS NUMBER		
			13-110	1.4.10 ³ - 10 ⁴	10 ⁴ - 10 ⁷
1.6	6.74E+02	1.63E+05	2.5-3	2.1-2.7	2-2.4
2.5	9.20E+02	2.23E+05			
3	1.06E+03	2.58E+05			

Table 9. Drag coefficient dependence on Reynolds number

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491

4.5 Test with sand

492

493 Tests with a sand bottom were carried out to investigate the effect of a sand bottom on the behaviour
494 of the catenary. Sand footprints (Figure 30) were generated during the tests due to the mooring lines
495 dragging over the seabed. As a consequence, these footprints increase the distance between the fairlead and
496 the bottom and, consequently, the tension is higher in these tests. Figure 31 shows the depth (in m) of the
497 footprints for each mooring line after the surge tests were performed. The most significant effects were
498 found for the surge movements. The influence of sand on the pitch and heave movements was more
499 attenuated. This was due to the necessity of dragging the catenary along the sea bottom for the surge tests,
500 while the heave and pitch tests have lifting processes which mitigate this effect.

Figure 30. Sand footprints generated by the mooring lines

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Figure 31. Depth of mooring line footprints

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The energy absorbed by the mooring line is represented in Figure 32 and Figure 33 for surge and heave movements, respectively. These results are compared with tests without sand in order to show the effects of sea bottom friction. In general, the energy absorbed in tests with sand is higher than in tests without sand, although some discrepancies were seen in the surge tests (period: 1.58 s). The least heavy chain is hardly influenced by the sea bottom friction. These effects are more significant for the shortest period due to slow mooring line movements over the seabed, resulting in reduced dynamic performance. Differences of between 4 % - 11 % in heave and 20 % - 75 % in surge were found for dynamic periods. The energy absorbed tends to be zero for long periods in both situations.

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Figure 32. Test: surge movement with and without sand. Comparison between the energy absorbed by the different lines

522
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Figure 33. Test: heave movement with and without sand. Comparison between the energy absorbed by the different lines

525 Finally, the hysteresis cycles for tests with and without sand are compared in order to show the
 526 distribution of energy (Figure 34). The hysteresis cycle shown belongs to the heaviest chain. The observed
 527 trend shows energy increasing at the maximum and minimum tensions. In addition, the maximum and
 528 minimum tensions are obtained at different positions with respect to the test without sand.

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Figure 34. Comparison between the hysteresis curves for the situations with and without sand.

532 The effects of the sand bottom on the mooring line tension show a similar pattern in all the tests. Sand
 533 increases and decreases the value of peaks and troughs, respectively, with respect to the situation without
 534 sand. The time series of tension on the fairlead for the heaviest mooring line are compared.

535 Figure 35 and Figure 37 show the case of the surge movement, with amplitude 75 mm / period 3.16 s ,
 536 and heave movement, with amplitude 75 mm / period 2.21 s. The shape of the tension wave shown is
 537 similar in both cases although with some differences in them, most particularly, in the crests and troughs.
 538 The maximum and minimum values of tension for surge and heave movements with and without sand are
 539 shown in Table 10 and Table 11. The more important differences are found in the dynamic periods (periods
 540 less than 2.25 s), up to 12 % in maximum tension, while for other periods the average between the
 541 percentage differences between the maximum and minimum tension is 2.5 % and 0.5 % respectively in
 542 surge and 1.9 % and 1.4 % respectively in heave. Finally, Figure 36 and Figure 38 represent the maximum
 543 and minimum tension values for each of the surge and heave tests, respectively. It is important to highlight
 544 that from a certain value of the period, in this case 2.25 s, tension values are practically constant, also
 545 decreasing the relative differences between the sand and no sand results.

Figure 35. Comparison of surge tension signals: with and without sand

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SURGE	Tension (N): 3 mm			
	Tmax		Tmin	
	In sand	Without sand	In sand	Without sand
0.79	20.390	18.260	0.413	0.237
1.58	10.140	9.968	3.444	3.595
2.37	8.923	8.626	4.555	4.598
3.16	8.900	8.751	4.455	4.481
4.74	9.263	9.030	4.349	4.375
6.32	9.404	9.175	4.326	4.344
7.91	9.543	9.247	4.328	4.329

Table 10. Maximum and minimum surge tension: with and without sand

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Figure 36. Test: surge movement with and without sand. Tension series

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Figure 37. Comparison of heave tension signals: with and without sand

HEAVE	Tension (N): 3 mm			
	Tmax		Tmin	
Period (s)	In sand	Without sand	In sand	Without sand
0.79	15.890	14.160	0.062	0.383
1.26	8.541	8.305	2.739	3.136
1.58	7.545	7.415	4.023	4.170
1.90	7.138	6.969	4.650	4.777
2.21	6.807	6.680	4.997	5.057
2.53	6.752	6.616	5.084	5.149
2.85	6.755	6.590	5.151	5.192
3.16	6.697	6.582	5.075	5.175
3.48	6.706	6.623	5.045	5.143

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Table 11. Maximum and minimum heave tension: with and without sand

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Figure 38. Test: heave movement with and without sand. Tension series

565 **5. Discussion**

566
567 The results have described the general answer of the mooring lines under different tests. However,
568 several explanations must be done.

569 Firstly, the stiffness of the mooring line was simulated with springs located and the end of the mooring
570 line. In general, this stiffness only works when the catenary is completely lifted. However, the catenaries
571 are designed for the anchor does not have vertical forces. For this reason, although the mooring lines tested
572 had springs they do not work during the tests. Nonetheless, the results obtained are validated due to the
573 weight has more importance in the behavior of the mooring lines.

574 Secondly, the energy absorbed and the tensions were analysed for different periods and imposed
575 movements. The results show the importance of acceleration on the mooring lines. Mooring lines are very
576 dynamics when movement periods are under 2.25 s being the drag and inertial forces relevants in the
577 behavior of the mooring lines. Movements with periods higher than 4 s show tensions practically constants
578 and accelerations negligible. The friction on the seabed was investigated using sand under the position of
579 mooring lines. The results of imposed movements in sand show the increase of tension and the energy
580 absorbed on the mooring lines.

581 Finally, test with wave and wave-current with the fairlead in static position were performed.
582 Uncertainties associated to the Reynolds number were found between the model and prototype. However,
583 the tensions show differences negligible with regard the static tension. Waves and imposed movements
584 were not tested by the lack of knowledge a priori of the influence of the waves in the movement of the
585 fairlead.

586 **6. Conclusions**

587
588 This paper presents a complete study to estimate the behavior of mooring lines by means of
589 experimental test campaign. The influence of several factors has been investigated: different weight of
590 mooring lines, imposed displacements, wave and current loads and friction coefficients.

591 An exhaustive study of mooring line acceleration was done in order to understand the influence of this
592 parameter on the energy absorbed, and on the movements and the tensions. For the heaviest chain, the
593 energy absorbed, the movements and the tensions all present small variations when movement periods are
594 longer than 2.25 s. Accelerations were less than 0.50 m/s^2 in the x-direction and less than 1 m/s^2 in the z-
595 direction in these cases. It is therefore possible to establish two different analysis; quasi-static analysis,
596 which is appropriate for determining the tension for low frequency displacements, and dynamic analysis,

597 which is suitable for high frequency displacements. Mooring line tensions and movements are related to
598 energy. A description of the evolution of the hysteresis cycle is included in this research.

599 Experiments with hydrodynamic forces (waves and wave and currents) prove that their effects on
600 mooring line dynamics are practically negligible. The dependence of drag coefficient as a function of the
601 Reynolds number was investigated.

602 In general, increases in the tension were obtained in tests with current, with higher differences being
603 obtained for the shortest period.

604 The effect of a sand bottom on the behaviour of a catenary was investigated. The results of the tests
605 showed increases in the energy absorbed and in the tensions in relation to the tests without sand. The most
606 significant differences were obtained for short periods. Differences in the energy absorbed of between 4
607 % - 11 % in heave and between 20 % - 75 % in surge were found. Regarding maximum tensions, differences
608 of 12 % in surge and heave were found, while for other periods the difference was 2.5 % in surge and 1.9
609 % in heave.

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